

Kaempferol as a Colorimetric Reagent for Determination of Zirconium

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Kaempferol (3,5, 7, 4'-tetrahydroxyflavone) reacts with zirconium in strongly acidic medium to form a yellow coloured complex. The system has been studied spectrophotometrically to determine the composition and other physical constants of the complex. The two components in the complex are present in equimolar ratio. The average value of the instability constant is 2.49×10^{-5} and the apparent molar extinction coefficient at 415 nm is $\sim 26,500$. The complex obeys Beer's law in the concentration range of 0.1 to 3.6 ppm of zirconium. The optimum range for determination of zirconium is 0.56 to 2.5 p.p.m. The sensitivity of the colour reaction is $0.003 \gamma \text{ Zr/Cm}^2 \equiv \log I_0/I \equiv 0.001$. The effect of foreign ions has been studied and interference due to some of them has been removed by using suitable masking agents.

A number of hydroxy flavones have been used as colorimetric reagents for the determination of zirconium^{1,6}. Kaempferol has been reported to give colour reactions with lanthanides⁷. It is observed that kaempferol also gives colour reactions with several ions, such as Th(IV), Mo(VI), U (IV), Se(III), Y(III), Ga(III), Ge(IV), Sb(III) and Zr(IV). Zirconium gives yellow colour which is much deeper than that of the ligand in acidic or neutral medium. This fact has been made the basis for the spectrophotometric determination of zirconium.

EXPERIMENTAL

Instruments and Reagents: A Unicam spectrophotometer, SP-600, with 10 m.m. transmission cells was used for absorbance measurements. A Perkin-Elmer Spectracord was employed to record the spectra during the preliminary investigations. Standard solutions of Zirconium (IV) were prepared by heating requisite amounts of $\text{ZrOCl}_2 \cdot 8\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (E. Merck, G. R.) in 10N-HCl on a boiling water bath for one hour. The solution was made 4N in hydrochloric acid (BDH, AnalaR) and standardised gravimetrically. Kaempferol was synthesised as reported in literature⁸. Stock solution of the ligand was prepared in 95% ethanol, by direct weighing and standard solutions were prepared by subsequent dilution of the stock solution with ethanol. All studies were carried out in 40%-ethanol as both the reagent and the complex are insoluble in water.

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SPECTROPHOTOMETRIC STUDIES: PRELIMINARY INVESTIGATIONS

(a) *Effect of Excess Reagent:* Solutions containing fixed amount of zirconium and varying amounts of ligand were prepared at 1N-acidity and absorbance measurements were made. From a plot of absorbance vs. varying amounts of the ligand, it was observed that a tenfold molar excess of the ligand is necessary to give almost constant absorbance values.

(b) *Effect of Time and Stability:* The absorbance values increase initially with time and become constant after a period of nearly seventy minutes. The complex is fairly stable and no change in absorbance values was detected even after keeping for twenty four hours.

Absorption Spectra: Absorption spectra of solutions containing zirconium and the ligand in different molar ratios were taken using identical reagent blanks. It was observed that there is only one absorption maximum under all the conditions ($\lambda_{\text{max}} = 415 \text{ nm}$) indicating thereby, the presence of only one complex species in solution (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Absorption Spectra of Zirconium-Kaempferol complex at 1N-HCl concentration vs reagent blank. Zirconium concentration = $2 \times 10^{-5} \text{M}$, 1. Kaempferol $1 \times 10^{-5} \text{M}$, 2. Kaempferol $2 \times 10^{-5} \text{M}$, 3. Kaempferol $4 \times 10^{-4} \text{M}$, 4. Kaempferol $2 \times 10^{-4} \text{M}$.

Effect of Acidity: Though the reaction can also be carried out in the presence of other acids, the use of hydrochloric acid is preferred due to the reasons mentioned elsewhere.^{2,9,10} Absorption spectra of solutions containing zirconium and ligand in the molar ratio 1:10 were recorded at varying acidities, the corresponding reagent blanks being employed in each case. It was observed that there is no shift in the nature of the curve by increasing the acid concentration up to 2N, beyond which the ligand becomes highly coloured. The absorbance of the complex remains practically constant in the acid concentration range 0.5 to 1N, beyond which it tends to decrease (Fig. 2).

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Fig. 2. Effect of Hydrochloric Acid concentration on Zirconium-Kaempferol Complex. $Zr=2 \times 10^{-5}M$; Kaempferol = $2 \times 10^{-4}M$. (1) $\lambda = 410-420 \text{ nm}$; (2) $\lambda = 430 \text{ nm}$; (3) $\lambda = 440 \text{ nm}$

PHYSICAL CONSTANTS:

(a) *Molar Composition*: The composition of the complex was evaluated by the method of continuous variations (Fig. 3) and the slope ratio methods, which indicate that zirconium and the reagent are present in equimolar ratio (1:1) in the complex. A tentative

Fig. 3. Composition by Job's Method. X ml. of Zr ($1 \times 10^{-4}M$) after acidification mixed with (5-X) ml of equimolar Kaempferol ($X=1$ to 4 ml). Total volume = 10.0 ml. Absorbance measured against corresponding reagent blank.

structure similar to that proposed by Grimaldi and White² can thus be assigned to the complex.

Beer's law, Sensitivity and Instability constant: It was observed that the complex conforms to Beer's law over the concentration range 0.1 to 3.6 p. p. m. The apparent molar extinction of the complex, calculated from Beer's law plot, is $\sim 26,500$ at 415 nm.

The sensitivity of the colour reaction is $0.003 \gamma \text{ Zr}/\text{Cm}^2$. $\log I_0/I = 0.001$. The optimum range of concentration obtained from Ringbom's plot¹¹ is 0.56 to 2.5 p.p.m. Zr.

The average value of instability constant, K, as calculated from the relationship:

$$K = \frac{\alpha^2 C}{(1 - \alpha)}$$

is 2.49×10^{-5} (where α is the degree of dissociation and C is the concentration of the complex in moles l^{-1}).

Recommended Procedure: To a solution, containing 0.1 to 2.5 p.p.m. Zr, is added hydrochloric acid, ethanol, excess of reagent and volume made up to 10ml. The medium should contain 40% ethanol and be 1N in hydrochloric acid. The absorbance is measured after 1 hr, at 415 nm, using the same concentration of the reagent as blank.

Effect of Diverse Ions: The effect of various ions in the determination of zirconium has been studied in a medium of 1N hydrochloric acid. To a solution containing 2.28 ppm of zirconium, several ions were added. Titanium (IV), molybdenum (VI), antimony (III), bismuth (III), yttrium, fluoride, thiocyanate, NTA and EDTA were found to interfere seriously. Acetate and sulphate were used to mark thorium(IV) and uranium (VI) in the determination of zirconium. The following ions were tolerated up to the amounts (in ppm) indicated within brackets: UO_2^{2+} (300), Th^{4+} (10), La^{3+} (50), Nd^{3+} (50), Pr^{3+} (50), Ce^{3+} (7), Al^{3+} (5), Fe^{2+} (25), Be^{2+} (60), Sc^{3+} (9), Cu^{2+} (50), Cd^{2+} (160), Ni^{2+} (200), Co^{2+} (170), Ba^{2+} (80), Zn^{2+} (100), Mn^{2+} (100), IO_3^- (2), PO_4^{3-} (5), $\text{C}_2\text{O}_4^{2-}$ (15), $\text{S}_2\text{O}_3^{2-}$ (3), $\text{B}_4\text{O}_7^{2-}$ (20), SO_4^{2-} (192), NO_3^- (1000), CH_3COO^- (700), $\text{C}_4\text{H}_4\text{O}_6^{2-}$ (50), $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{O}_7^{3-}$ (50).

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